

THIN-FILM PIEZOELECTRIC TRANSFORMERS OPERATING IN HARMONICS OF OUT-OF-PLANE FLEXURE MODES

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ABSTRACT

This paper documents disc-shaped flexure-mode piezoelectric transformers constructed with 0.5 μm lead-zirconate-titanate (PZT) on 4- μm silicon resonators. The transformers are electrode shaped to excite out-of-plane flexure modes at ~ 12 , ~ 34 , and ~ 63 MHz. The incorporation of silicon enables the excitation of out-of-plane flexural modes which exploit large quasi-static material coupling factors (using both e_{31} and e_{32}). Transformer efficiencies $>50\%$ with $\sim 5\text{X}$ open-circuit voltage gains are predicted. Experimental transformer figures of merit equivalent to previously-reported extensional modes [1] are demonstrated with 3X-13X size reductions. Electromechanical coupling factors, k_{eff}^2 , of 3.4% exceed those measured for extensional modes (with 4 μm silicon) by $\sim 3.5\text{X}$.

KEYWORDS

MEMS piezoelectric transformers, chip-scale power supplies, PZT-MEMS resonant transformers, RF sensors

INTRODUCTION

Chip-scale power supplies motivate the need for high-frequency, on-chip passive elements to achieve significant size reduction. Applications motivating this research area include point-of-load converters in microprocessors [2], inverters for solid-state lighting and solar-energy harvesting, as well as power management for wearable energy harvesters and future micro-autonomous / micro-robotics systems technologies [3,4]. These applications need power management units with large power densities and motivate high inductance and / or capacitance density power passives, components typically limiting the size / volume of the converter. Other applications motivating RF voltage transformers include zero-power-consuming RF sensors for unattended sensor applications (e.g. DARPA N-ZERO).

The vision of replacing traditional lumped-element inductors, magnetic transformers, and capacitors used in resonant converter approaches motivates this work. Electromechanical resonators and transformers feature a number of advantages over their traditional magnetic counterparts: large energy/power densities, absence of electromagnetic noise, large inductance densities, and frequency selectivity with narrow bandwidth [5-8]. In the 10's-100's MHz range, magnetic-materials based inductors with quality factors, Q , exceeding 10 have been limited [9]. For inductors with $Q > 10$, the inductance densities are limited to $< 200 \text{ nH/mm}^2$ [10]. In contrast, thin-film electromechanical resonators and transformers offer

extremely high equivalent electromechanical inductance densities (e.g. $> 100,000 \text{ nH/mm}^2$ at 14-20 MHz frequency [8]), but there are still challenges in maintaining the product of quality factor (unloaded) and electromechanical coupling factor, $k_{\text{eff}}^2 Q_u$, which has a direct impact on device efficiency and voltage gain [1].

Although there have been significant prior art detailing thin-film piezoelectric resonators for RF filters, there has been limited work on thin-film MEMS piezoelectric transformers (piezo-transformers) [1], [11-15]. While this work builds upon prior electrode shaping methods used for thin-film PZT resonators [16], it does contrast prior thin-film PZT piezoelectric transformer work relying on the use of the typical extensional modes presented in the MEMS literature [1] and utilized with bulk-scale piezo-transformers [17]. Herein, flexure-mode devices are explored and feature asymmetric electrodes needed for impedance, voltage, or current transformation. Low motional impedances are demonstrated at moderate frequencies using these out-of-plane flexural modes with piezoelectric multi-layer composites. The excitation of these modes utilizes strong quasi-static material coupling factors (using both e_{31} and e_{32} stress constants instead of only e_{31} with extensional modes) resulting in enhanced effective electromechanical coupling factors, k_{eff}^2 , which directly impacts transformer performance. Experimental results on three different out-of-plane flexure harmonic designs and their predicted load-dependent transformer performances are presented. Additionally, the first demonstration of a parallel combination of MEMS transformers to achieve power load matching is also documented.

MEMS PIEZOTRANSFORMER DESIGN

Mechanical Design and Electrode Shaping

This work explores harmonics of flexure modes in disc-shaped geometries. The incorporation of device silicon renders an asymmetric stack and the ability to efficiently excite out-of-plane flexure modes. The excitation of these modes is achieved through proper electrode shaping techniques, which is detailed in prior art [16]. This technique determines electrode shapes based on force- and charge-cancellation assessment over an electrode region with arbitrarily shaped geometries and mode shapes. The technique determines sufficient shapes to strongly excite the mode of interest and compares the induced piezoelectric stresses with the modal principle stresses to determine the local suitability of electrode placement.

The three resonant devices explored are based on the $i,j = 1,1$, $1,2$ and $1,3$ modes, where the i,j indices indicate the number of nodal diameters and nodal circles, respectively.

Figure 1 shows the fabricated devices, constructed with $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ PZT on $4\ \mu\text{m}$ silicon, as well as ANSYS results depicting the mode shapes. The resonant frequencies, f_r , are simulated to be 12.1, 33.6, and 62.7 MHz for Discs 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

Figure 1: Mode shapes (left) simulated in ANSYS and micrographs (middle) of fabricated, two-port PZT on $4\ \mu\text{m}$ Si piezo-transformers. Ports 1 (P1) and 2 (P2) are labeled.

Piezoelectric Transformer Equivalent Circuit

The equivalent circuits of the piezoelectric transformer with and without a resistive load, R_L , are shown (Fig. 2). C_{in} and C_{out} are the input and output capacitances, respectively, while L_m , R_m , and C_m are the motional inductance, resistance and capacitance, respectively. For piezoelectric transformers, the efficiencies and voltage gains are load-dependent because of the inherent reactive and capacitive nature of the device's output port [15]. Voltage gains > 1 are possible due to this reactive nature of the load. The peak in efficiency occurs when the real part of the reactive load, $R_{L,real}$ (the real part of the series equivalent of C_{out} and R_L in Fig. 2b), is at its maximum. The peak efficiency is

$$\eta_{peak} = \frac{1}{1 + 2\omega_{max} C_{out} R_m} = \frac{1}{1 + 2/TxFOM} \quad (1)$$

while the open-circuit voltage gain is

$$V_{Gain,oc} = \left| \frac{V_{out}(j\omega_{max})}{V_{in}(j\omega_{max})} \right|_{oc} \cong \frac{1}{\omega_{max} R_m C_{out}} = TxFOM \quad (2)$$

where ω_{max} is the frequency corresponding to maximum circuit efficiency (which is slightly different than the resonant frequency, ω_r , of the piezoelectric resonator without a resistive load) while $TxFOM$ is the transformer figure of merit. This term is defined in order to conveniently compare transformers of varying materials, composites, modes, geometries and frequencies. $TxFOM$ is dependent on but not equivalent to the $ResFOM = k_{eff}^2 Q_u$, a one-port equivalent measurement of performance typically used for filtering applications [18]; it is also asymmetric and dependent on the excitation port.

Equivalent Circuit of Transformers in Parallel

Additionally, parallel equivalent devices are considered in this work for the Disc-2 design, where three of these

Figure 2: Piezo-transformer equivalent circuits (a) without and (b) with a resistive load.

designs are electrically in parallel (Fig. 3). Although this should improve insertion loss in a $50\text{-}\Omega$ system, which is confirmed in the measurement section below, the peak efficiency and open-circuit voltage gain should remain equivalent (assuming negligible routing losses) when compared with the non-parallel, Disc-2 design. Although the equivalent R_m of three devices in parallel is improved by a factor of 3, this comes at the cost of a 3X increase in capacitance to ground at the output port, C_{out}^* , in Fig. 3. Therefore, equivalent $TxFOMs$ should result with the Disc-2 and Disc-2-parallel designs.

The reason for considering a parallel approach is to increase efficiency, or shift the peak in efficiency, at low-resistive power loads or higher-current loads. For the Disc-2-parallel case, the R_L corresponding to peak efficiency is

$$R_{L,\eta_{peak}} = \frac{1}{\omega_{max} 3C_{out}} \quad (3)$$

and 3X lower than the R_L at peak efficiency for the Disc-2 device type. This also subsequently changes the R_L values corresponding to the peak in power delivery. This can be further understood when assessing the case when $R_{L,real}$ is equivalent to the combined motional resistances. Further details can be found in [15], [19].

Figure 3: (a) Micrograph of the three parallel Disc-2 type devices (Disc2-parallel) and (b) equivalent circuit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two-Port Measurements

The devices were fabricated in a thin-film PZT MEMS process which is previously documented [16]. Scattering parameter measurements (Fig. 4) were taken with a 10-V-DC bias superimposed on the input and output ports. The relevant resonant transformer metrics are summarized in Table-1. Motional resistances, R_m , range between 122 and $162\ \Omega$ with a 2-8.9 range in $ResFOM$. Figure 5 reveals the cross-wafer variation in $ResFOM$ and corresponding R_m 's. The variations are due to inconsistencies in the fabrication process resulting in unintended device silicon undercut.

Figure 4: Two-port scattering parameter measurements of the three disc types including Disc-2-parallel.

Table 1: Piezoelectric transformer devices' measurement results summary including resonant frequency, f_r , motional resistance, R_m , unloaded Q factor, Q_u , effective electro-mechanical coupling factor, k_{eff}^2 , ResFOM, capacitance at port 1, C_1 , and capacitance at port 2, C_2 . *Note: total parallel equivalent values reported (see Fig. 3).

Device	f_r [Mz]	Q_u	R_m [Ω]	k_{eff}^2 [%]	ResFOM $k_{eff}^2 Q_u$	C_1 [pF]	C_2 [pF]
Disc-1	11.8	263	139	3.4	8.9	22	23
Disc-2	33.0	264	122	1.7	3.9	22	7.8
Disc-2-parallel	33.0	--	53*	--	--	80*	21*
Disc-3	63.2	261	162	0.8	2.0	27	8.4

Figure 5: Cross-wafer variation in ResFOM and R_m .

Predicted Piezoelectric Transformer Performance

The simulated transformer performances for the Disc-2 and Disc-2-parallel types are compared in Fig. 6 with peak efficiencies and open-circuit voltage gains dependent on the excitation port. As expected, when the input drive capacitance, C_{in} , is greater than the output capacitance, C_{out} , the resulting peak efficiencies and open-circuit voltage gains are greater. When comparing the two design types, similar efficiency peaks of $\sim 55\%$ result, however, the corresponding resistive load at peak efficiency, $R_{L,peak}$ differ by a factor of 2X (with $C_{in} > C_{out}$), which is not the expected 3X. This is largely due to the differences in routing resistances at the output port which has a direct impact on the electrical quality factor of the effective load and the

transformer performance; this impact has been previously documented [1]. A summary of expected performances for the four different device types is shown in Table 2. When exciting P1 of all of the devices, the simulated peak efficiencies range between 41% and 55% while the corresponding $R_{L,peak}$ vary due to the varying C_{out} . The open-circuit voltage gains are approximately equivalent to the TxFOMs of 4.2, 5, 4.2 and 1.8 for the Disc-1, -2, -2-parallel, and -3 devices, respectively. The expected results with P2 as the excitation port are different and worse than with P1. This occurs because $C_1 > C_2$ for these asymmetric-electrode device designs (except for Disc-1 which has a symmetric electrode design) and results in degraded TxFOMs.

Figure 6: Expected R_L -dependent piezo-transformer performance for (top) Disc-2 and (bottom) Disc-2-parallel devices (excitation port indicated in the legend).

Table 2: Summary of expected piezoelectric transformer performances amongst the designs with different excitation ports. Note: Disc-1 is a symmetric device and does not exhibit asymmetry in the transformer performance.

Device	P1 input			P2 input		
	$V_{Gain,oc}$ [V/V]	η_{peak} [%]	$R_{L,\eta_{peak}}$ [Ω]	$V_{Gain,oc}$ [V/V]	η_{peak} [%]	$R_{L,\eta_{peak}}$ [Ω]
Disc-1	4.7	55	350	--	--	--
Disc-2	4.3	55	220	2.5	34	130
Disc-2-parallel	4.8	54	110	2.8	32	50
Disc-3	1.9	41	160	1.2	22	90

Comparison with Extensional-mode Transformers

In Fig. 7 the TxFOMs for the current devices are compared with length-extensional PZT-on-Si transformers previously reported [1]. The prior work explored harmonics of length-extensional modes with $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ PZT on silicon devices and resonant frequencies between 14 and 19 MHz; the device silicon thicknesses assessed were 2, 4, and

10 μm . The flexure modes in this work exhibit similar $T_x\text{FOMs}$ but with a 3X-13X reduction in device area. The flexure modes also exhibit $\sim 3.5\text{X}$ maximum improvement in k_{eff}^2 (see Table 1) over the 4 μm -silicon extensional-modes (with k_{eff}^2 ranging between 0.76-0.97%) previously reported.

Figure 7: Measured $T_x\text{FOM}$ of the flexure-mode disc-type transformers of this work compared with prior work using length-extensional PZT-on-silicon transformers.

CONCLUSION

MEMS piezoelectric transformers are explored using harmonics of flexure modes in disc-shaped geometries. The PZT on silicon stack enables excitation of these out-of-plane flexure modes, which cannot be exploited in symmetric PZT stacks. Two-port scattering parameter measurements reveal devices with expected transformer efficiencies up to 55% and open-circuit voltage gains as high as 4.8. This work also compares transformer figures of merit with previously-reported extensional-mode piezoelectric transformers operating with common modes reported in prior resonator and piezo-transformer literature. This work reveals that flexure-modes in discs are viable modes for use in MEMS piezoelectric transformer applications.

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